

Appendix

A Experimental Settings

All experiments are conducted using the PyTorch framework on an NVIDIA RTX 4090 GPU. We train various components under different settings as summarized below.

Training Settings

Component	Epochs
Client Classifiers (Teacher)	100
Global Server Classifier (Student)	100
Feature Extractor	100
Rectified Flow Model (HAM10000)	700
Rectified Flow Model (Other Datasets)	800
Baseline Methods	100

Table 1: Training epochs for different components.

Model Architecture and Design

Aspect	Setting
Classifier Backbone	ResNet-18 (trained from scratch)
ResNet-18 Pretrained Weights	Not used (natural image weights unsuitable)
Image Input and Generation Resolution	224×224
Feature Alignment Strategy	Third-layer features of Resnet-18 (Teacher-Student)

Table 2: Model architecture details.

Optimization Details

Module	Optimizer Configuration
Rectified Flow Model	Adam, learning rate = 5e-4
Other components (e.g., classifiers)	Adam, learning rate = 1e-4, weight decay = 1e-5

Table 3: Optimizer settings for different training modules.

B Synthetic image visualization

We provide synthetic feature-level images generated by our proposed method for all datasets. The results demonstrate that these images closely resemble the original data distribution while intentionally omitting some image details to ensure privacy protection.

Brain Tumor Classification Dataset

Category: Glioma

Figure 1: Example synthetic glioma from the brain tumor classification dataset.

Category: Meningioma

Figure 2: Example synthetic meningioma from the brain tumor classification dataset.

Category: Pituitary

Figure 3: Example synthetic pituitary from the brain tumor classification dataset.

Category: No tumor

Figure 4: Example synthetic no tumor images from the brain tumor classification dataset.

Chest X-Ray Tuberculosis Dataset

Category: Normal

Figure 5: Example synthetic normal images from the chest x-ray tuberculosis dataset.

Category: Tuberculosis

Figure 6: Example synthetic tuberculosis images from the chest x-ray tuberculosis dataset.

HAM10000 Dataset

Category: Benign keratosis-like lesions

Figure 7: Example synthetic benign keratosis-like lesions from the HAM10000 dataset.

Category: Dermatofibroma

Figure 8: Example synthetic dermatofibroma from the HAM10000 dataset.

Category: Melanoma

Figure 9: Example synthetic melanoma from the HAM10000 dataset.

Category: Vascular lesions

Figure 10: Example synthetic vascular lesions from the HAM10000 dataset.

Category: Basal cell carcinoma

Figure 11: Example synthetic basal cell carcinoma from the HAM10000 dataset.

Category: Melanocytic nevi

Figure 12: Example synthetic melanocytic nevi from the HAM10000 dataset.

Category: Actinic keratoses and intraepithelial carcinoma

Figure 13: Example synthetic actinic keratoses and intraepithelial carcinoma from the HAM10000 dataset.